

CREATING THE UNDERSTANDING OF PUPILS AND STUDENTS ABOUT
ATHLETICS

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Abstract: This article provides complete information about athletics for school and vocational school students.

Key words: athletics, Queen of Sports, Olympics, stadium, game, running, high jump, javelin throw.

Athletics is known as the "Queen of Sports" and it is one of the most amazing and popular sports. Today we have collected some interesting facts related to its history.

1. The date of appearance of athletics corresponds to 776 BC. It was then that the first running competitions were held at the Olympic Games in ancient Greece.

2. In athletics, it was not always possible to start from the bottom. Before 1887, before the start, the runners simply waited for the order. That all changed when Sprinter Sherrill observed the kangaroo's movements and suggested a new situation.

3. At the Olympic Games in Berlin in 1936, Japanese athletes Shuhei Nisida and Sueo Oe showed the same result and both took second place. But the Japan Sports Federation awarded Oe a bronze medal. After returning home, the athletes melted down their medals and made new silver and bronze medals.

4. In the first Olympic Games, the length of the marathon constantly varied from 40 km to 42.75 km. The modern standard of 42 kilometers 195 meters was established as the distance of the games held in London in 1908.

5. Two-time Olympic champion in the 10,000 meters, Haile Gebreselassie of Ethiopia, had a unique look when running: his left arm was pressed against his body and his body was slightly bent. The athlete himself explains this by the fact that he runs 10 kilometers to school every morning with books in his left hand on his lap and returns home in the evening.

6. Murray Halberg, a New Zealand runner, played rugby when he was young, but in one of the games he suffered a serious injury that left his left arm paralyzed. But Murray decided not to quit the sport and started running. Her willpower led her to a gold medal in the 5,000 meters at the 1960 Rome Olympics.

7. The word "stadium" is applied to the place where the 192-meter race was run at the first Olympic Games in 776 BC and comes from the ancient Greek word "stadium" ("stages").

8. The first winner of the aforementioned running distance was the chef. His name was Coreb of Elis.

Athletics is one of the most popular types of sports; includes running at various distances, athletic walking, high jump, long jump, triple jump, javelin throw, javelin throw, javelin throw, shot put, all-around (squatting, heptathlon) exercises. There are more than 50 exercises in athletics, 48 of which are included in the program of the Olympic Games (at the 2000 Sydney Olympics, men competed in 23 types of athletics, and women competed in 20). In addition, athletics is an exercise of modern pentathlon and triathlon sports, it is included in the program of training of all sports, educational, military-preparatory, health exercises, "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" sports tests of students and young people. Homer's "Iliad", Ibn Sina's "Laws of Medicine" and other books contain information about athletics exercises. In the ancient Olympic Games (from 776 BC to 394 BC) competitions were organized mainly in Athletics.

In the development of modern athletics in the 19th century, competitions in England (from 1837), all-Greek games in Athens (from 1859) and the revival Olympics (from 1896) were of great importance. The International Amateur Athletics Federation (IAAF) was established in 1912, with 200 member countries (2001; Uzbekistan Athletics Federation has been a member since 1993). The IAAF has been holding the World Cup (now Grand Prix) since 1977, and the World Championship since 1983. Interest in athletics in Uzbekistan increased after the establishment of a stadium adapted to this type in Margilon in 1885. Athletics competitions were held in Tashkent in 1902, national championships in 1919, spartakia in 1927. In Uzbekistan, more than 135,000 people are engaged in athletics under more than 140 coaches, 3 of the coaches have the title of honored athlete of Uzbekistan, 10 of them have the title of honored sports teacher of Uzbekistan (2001). Track and field athletes from Uzbekistan have been participating in the Olympic Games since 1952. At the Olympics, Marina Shmonina (4x100 m relay race, 1992) won a gold medal, Rodion Gataulin (pole vault, 1988) won a silver medal, Ramil Ganiyev (running, 1996) took 8th place. Oleg Ryakhovsky (triple jump), Roza Babich (200 m hurdles) and Tatyana Biryulina (javelin throw) broke the world record. Ashur Normurodov (long, distance running) was a three-time former All-Union champion (1967-69). At the Asian Games in 1994, Svetlana Munkova (high jump), Ramil Ganiyev (jump), Oksana Yarigina (javelin), in 1998 Oleg Veretelnikov (jump), Sergei Voinov (javelin) were awarded gold medals. Track and field USA, Great Britain, well developed in countries such as Germany, Cuba, China.

Modern athletics began to take shape in England earlier than in other countries. In the 18th century, running on hippodromes and distances between cities became popular. In 1770, a one-hour run was 17 km 300 meters. In 1803, a runner named D. Todd ran the distance from Goshd to Parkidon, Okebridge Roy, in 1 h 10 min.

In the middle of the 18th century, competitions were held between college students and university students. In 1837, the first competitions of Resby college students took place in a 2 km run. Soon, college students from Eton, Oxford, Cambridge, London and other cities joined their initiative. Then they started running short distances, running over hurdles and

throwing heavy objects into the competition program. Since 1851, running, high jump and long jump have been included in the competition program. Later, athletics competitions started to become a picture in universities. Oxford and Cambridge universities took the initiative in this regard. In 1864, for the first time, an athletics competition between these educational institutions took place, and then such competitions were held every year. In 1866, the first Anguilla championship was held. In the 60s, adults also became interested in athletics. English aristocrats were interested in athletics, but they did not want to be with the common people on the treadmills. In particular, they could not afford to lose to the representatives of the "lower" class, who occasionally managed to participate in the so-called open competitions from running and jogging. In this regard, in 1864, sports clubs of Anguilla adopted the "amateur" statute, preventing aristocrats and working people from meeting on the treadmills. Based on this regulation, representatives of physical labor will be declared professionals and will not be allowed to enter amateur sports clubs and participate in competitions with amateurs. In 1865, the London Athletic Club was founded, and it began to popularize athletics. This club held national championships in athletics and monitored compliance with the rules of amateurism. In 1880, the Amateur Athletics Association was founded in England, which became the highest body in athletics in the British Empire. It unites in Anglia all the bourgeois athletics clubs in its dominions and colonies. The association is responsible for general management of athletics. Anguilla prepares athletes to participate in international competitions. The development of athletics in France began in 1879, first of all in military and civilian (citizen) schools. Starting from 1880, running competitions were regularly held on the streets. At the end of 1880, the French bourgeoisie formed the association of French athletic societies. In the second half of the century, athletics began to develop in the United States. The development of athletics in the USA begins in 1868, when the New York Athletic Club was founded and the first athletics competition was held. Universities will soon become the center of development of athletics. In 1874, he won the first athletics competition at Howard University. In the 1980s, the "National Association of American Amateur Athletics", which is an intercollegiate athletics union, and the "American Amateur Athletics Association", the governing body of athletics in the country, were formed. The first professional runners appeared in America, as well as in England. professional runner C. Rowell ran 144 km 64 m in 12 hours. The first indoor track and field competition was held in New York in 1868 at the Emneyer ring arena. This competition was the predecessor of the Anguilla program. 1871 in America the university championship was In 1875, the first national championship was held. At the same time, the development of athletics in the United States and England began to spread widely from other European countries. First in France, then in Germany, Scandinavian countries began to spread widely. The first athletics competitions in Germany were organized in 1888 by football clubs in Berlin. Independent athletics clubs appeared in the 1890s. In 1898, the governing organization of athletics, the German Athletics Administration, was established. In the Scandinavian countries, athletics as an independent sport began to appear in Sweden in 1887, in Norway in 1897 and in Finland in 1906. Athletics began to develop as a sport in Hungary, Poland, Czechoslovakia, Yugoslavia and other Central European countries. In many countries, it is accepted as a sport of athletics. The revival of the ancient Greek Olympic

Games was of great importance in the development of athletics. In 1895, a gymnastics competition similar to the Olympic Games was held in Athens. Many types of athletics were included in the competition program.

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